

Kinetics of Oxidation of α -Aminoacids by Sodium N-Chloro-4 Methyl Benzene Sulphonamide in Perchloric Acid Medium

H. M. K. NAIDU, S. N. KATGERI and D. S. MAHADEVAPPA*

Department of Post-graduate Studies and Research in Chemistry, Manasagangotri University of Mysore, Mysore-570 006

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A kinetic study of oxidation of leucine, serine, glutamine and glutamic acid by Sodium-N-Chloro-4 methyl benzene sulphonamide or Chloramine-T (CAT) in presence of HClO_4 has been made at 30° . The reaction shows first order dependence each on CAT and amino acid and is inverse first order with respect to H^+ ion. Ionic strength and presence of the added reaction product, *p*-toluenesulphonamide have no effect on the rate. Chloride ion catalyses the reaction. The reaction was studied at different temperatures and the activation parameters have been evaluated. A mechanism in which the zwitterion interacts with protonated CAT has been proposed to account for the observed kinetics.

SODIUM-N-chloro-4 methyl benzene sulphonamide or Chloramine-T ($p\text{-CH}_3\text{-C}_6\text{H}_4\text{SO}_2\text{NClNa}\cdot 3\text{H}_2\text{O}$) behaves as an oxidising agent both in acid and alkaline media¹. This organic compound containing positive halogen undergoes a two electron change in its reactions. The oxidation potential of chloramine-T/sulphonamide system is pH dependent and decreases with increase in pH of the medium². Chloramine-T (CAT) is of special interest for studying reaction mechanisms as it behaves both as chlorinating and oxidising agent. It furnishes different types of reactive species in solution, such as monochloramine-T, (RNHCl where $\text{R} = p\text{-CH}_3\text{C}_6\text{H}_4\text{SO}_2$), dichloramine-T (RNCl_2) and HOCl , depending on pH of the medium. Free chlorine has been detected in strong acid medium in presence of chloride ion.

Although oxidation of bio-organic compounds by CAT has been reported, only a few reactions of amino acids in alkaline medium³ have been studied from a kinetic view point. As a part of our kinetic studies of chloraminometric reactions in acid medium⁴ we report our detailed investigations of oxidation of leucine, serine, glutamine and glutamic acid by CAT in presence of perchloric acid.

Experimental

All solutions were prepared in triply distilled water. Chloramine-T (E. Merck) was purified by the method of Morris *et al*⁵. An aqueous solution of the compound was iodometrically standardised and preserved in brown bottles to prevent its photochemical deterioration.

Leucine, serine, glutamine and glutamic acid (Centron Research Lab., Bombay, India) were found

to be chromatographically pure. They were further assayed by the acetous perchloric acid method⁶. All other reagents were of accepted grades of purity. The ionic strength of the reaction mixture was kept constant at a high value with a concentrated solution of sodium perchlorate.

The reaction was carried out in glass stoppered pyrex boiling tubes. Requisite amounts of the amino acid, HClO_4 and NaClO_4 solutions and water (to maintain total volume constant for all runs), were taken in the tube and thermostated at 30° . A measured amount of CAT solution also at the same temperature was added to the mixture and progress of the reaction was followed by an iodometric estimation of the unreacted CAT in a measured aliquot of the reaction mixture at various time intervals. The course of the reaction was studied for two-half lives. The pseudo first order rate constants calculated were reproducible within $\pm 2.0\%$.

Stoichiometry :

Varying ratios of amino acid to CAT were mixed in presence of HClO_4 ($\sim 0.5M$) at room temperature. Estimation of unreacted CAT after twenty-four hours showed that one mole of serine consumes three moles of CAT and one mole of leucine, glutamine or glutamic acid requires two moles of the oxidant :

* To whom communications should be made.

Paper chromatography was used to identify the sulphonamide. Benzyl alcohol saturated with water was used as the solvent with 0.5% vanillin in 1% HCl solution in ethanol as the spray reagent ($R_F=0.905$). The nitriles were identified by their colour reaction with hydroxylamine and ferric chloride⁷. The cyanate formed was detected by Werner's test⁸.

Results and Discussion

The kinetics of oxidation of amino acids by CAT was investigated at several initial concentrations of

TABLE 1—EFFECT OF CONCENTRATION OF REACTANTS ON THE REACTION RATE AT 30°C

[H⁺]=0.05M for leucine and glutamine, 0.03M for serine and 0.01M for glutamic acid $\mu=0.500M$

Amino acids	[CAT]M	[Amino acid]M	$k_1 \times 10^4 \text{ sec}^{-1}$	$k_2 \text{ mole}^{-1} \text{ lit. sec}^{-1}$
(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)	(5)
Leucine	0.003	0.02	1.44	7.201×10^{-2}
	0.003	0.025	1.89	7.544×10^{-2}
	0.003	0.035	2.69	7.686×10^{-2}
	0.003	0.040	2.98	7.449×10^{-2}
	0.003	0.060	4.10	6.848×10^{-2}
	0.003	0.03	2.54	8.467×10^{-2}
	0.0025	0.03	2.55	
	0.003	0.03(a)	2.56	
	0.0035	0.03	2.57	
	0.004	0.03	2.61	
Serine	0.003*	0.03	2.56	
	0.003**	0.03	2.49	
	0.003	0.01	1.44	1.441×10^{-2}
	0.003	0.02	2.81	1.404×10^{-2}
	0.003	0.03(a)	4.25	1.417×10^{-2}
	0.003	0.04	6.86	1.465×10^{-2}
	0.003	0.05	7.29	1.453×10^{-2}
	0.001	0.03	4.22	1.406×10^{-2}
	0.002	0.03	4.16	
	0.004	0.03	4.11	
Glutamine	0.005	0.03	4.08	
	0.003*	0.03	4.22	
	0.003**	0.03	4.24	
	0.003	0.05(a)	2.66	5.318×10^{-3}
	0.003	0.03	2.60	5.330×10^{-3}
	0.003	0.04	2.05	5.118×10^{-3}
	0.003	0.06	3.23	5.385×10^{-3}
	0.003	0.08	4.22	5.278×10^{-3}
	0.001	0.05	2.65	
	0.002	0.05	2.58	
Glutamic acid	0.001	0.05	2.69	
	0.005	0.05	2.71	
	0.003*	0.05	2.65	
	0.003**	0.05	2.70	
	0.001	0.03(a)	3.99	
	0.002	0.03	3.98	
	0.003	0.03	4.00	
	0.004	0.03	3.91	
	0.005	0.03	3.88	
	0.001	0.015	2.16	1.440×10^{-2}
0.001	0.03	3.99	1.330×10^{-2}	
0.001	0.04	4.88	1.220×10^{-2}	
0.001	0.05	6.94	1.388×10^{-2}	
0.001	0.06	8.30	1.883×10^{-2}	
0.001*	0.03	4.04		
0.001**	0.03	3.99		

* When $\mu=2.0M$.
 ** In presence of excess of TSA.
 (a) Standard runs.

the reactants. At constant [H⁺], with the substrate in large excess the pseudo first order rate constant k_1 increase with [amino acid] and a first order dependence on the substrate concentration is noted (Table 1) (Fig. 1). The rate decreases with increasing [HClO₄] (Table 2). A plot of $\log k_1$ vs $\log [H^+]$ gives a straight line with slope, -1 (Fig. 2).

Fig. 1. Plot of $\log k_1$ Vs [Amino acid].
 (a) leucine, (b) serine, (c) glutamine and (d) glutamic acid. Scale A is for serine (b), glutamine (c), and leucine (a). Scale B is for glutamic acid (d).
 [CAT]=0.003M for leucine, serine and glutamine and 0.001M for glutamic acid.
 [H⁺]=0.05M for leucine and glutamine, 0.03M for serine and 0.01M for glutamic acid.
 $\mu=0.5M$; Temperature=30°.

TABLE 2—EFFECT OF ACID CONCENTRATION ON THE REACTION RATE AT 30°C

[Amino acid]=0.03M for leucine, serine and glutamic acid, 0.05M for glutamine; [CAT]=0.003M for leucine, serine and glutamine, 0.001M for glutamic acid $\mu=0.500M$

Amino acid	[H ⁺]M	$k_1 \times 10^4 \text{ sec}^{-1}$	$10^4 k_1 [H^+] \text{ mole}^{-1} \text{ sec}^{-1}$
(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)
Leucine	0.03	4.19	1.26
	0.05	2.56	1.28
	0.06	2.14	1.28
	0.07	1.88	1.32
Serine	0.08	1.60	1.28
	0.03	4.25	1.28
	0.04	3.11	1.24
	0.05	2.55	1.28
Glutamine	0.06	1.97	1.18
	0.08	1.47	1.18
	0.025	5.43	1.36
	0.03	4.57	1.37
Glutamic acid	0.05	2.66	1.33
	0.06	2.29	1.37
	0.075	1.82	1.33
	0.10	1.34	1.34

(Table 2 Contd.)

	0.005	7.79	0.39
	0.006	6.59	0.39
Glutamic acid	0.007	5.86	0.39
	0.009	4.36	0.39
	0.010	3.99	0.39

 Fig. 2. Plot of $\log k_1$ Vs $\log [H^+]$

(a) leucine, (b) serine, (c) glutamine and (d) glutamic acid.

*[CAT]=0.003M for leucine, serine and glutamine and 0.001M for glutamic acid.

[Amino Acid]=0.03M for leucine, serine and glutamic acid and 0.05M for glutamine.

*Scale A for serine (b) and glutamine (d);

Scale B for leucine (a) and Scale C for glutamic acid (c)

$\mu=0.5M$; Temperature=30°.

The reaction was studied at different temperatures and the activation parameters have been evaluated (Table 3).

 TABLE 3—THERMODYNAMIC PARAMETERS FOR THE OXIDATION OF α -AMINO ACIDS BY CHLORAMINE-T IN $HClO_4$ MEDIUM

Amino acids	ΔH^\ddagger KJ mol ⁻¹	ΔS^\ddagger JK ⁻¹
Leucine	83.92 ± 0.01	-28.87 ± 0.01
Serine	99.28 ± 0.03	+22.33 ± 0.03
Glutamine	86.28 ± 0.01	-23.28 ± 0.02
Glutamic acid	67.36 ± 0.02	-22.06 ± 0.02

Concentrations of the reagents as in the standard runs (Table 1)

Effect of changing the solvent composition :

Addition of methanol to the reaction mixture decreases the rate. A plot of $\log k_{obs}$ vs $1/D$ where D is the dielectric constant gives a straight line with a negative slope (Fig. 3).

 Fig. 3. Plot of $\log k_1$ Vs $1/D$

(a) leucine, (b) serine, (c) glutamine and (d) glutamic acid.

[CAT]=0.003M for leucine, serine and glutamine; and 0.001M for glutamic acid.

[Amino acid]=0.03M for leucine, serine and glutamic acid and 0.05M for glutamine.

[H⁺]=0.05M for leucine and glutamine, 0.03M for serine and 0.01M for glutamic acid.

$\mu=0.5M$; Temperature=30°.

The experimental rate law is of the form :

$$-\frac{d}{dt} [CAT] = k \frac{[CAT][Amino\ acid]}{[H^+]} \quad \dots (1)$$

Chloramine-T is a strong electrolytes⁹. (RNCINa, where $R=p-CH_3C_6H_4SO_2$) and the anion can be protonated in acid solutions (Equation 2). The free acid can undergo disproportionation and/or hydrolysis (Equations 3 and 4).

Thus in acidified CAT solutions, the probable oxidising species are RNHCl, RNCl₂ (dichloramine-T) and HOCl. If RNCl₂ were to be the reactive species, then the rate law predicts a second order dependence of rate on CAT, which is contrary to the experimental observations. Ionic strength of the medium has no effect (Table 1) on the rate indicating that neutral species are involved in the rate determining step. Equation (4) indicates that the hydrolysis is slight and if HOCl is involved, a first order retardation of rate by added toluene sulphonamide is expected. However no such effect was noted. (Table 3) First approximation calculations by Bishop and Jennings¹⁰ on decinormal solutions of CAT have shown that [RNHCl] and [HOCl] are ~10⁻² and 10⁻⁷M respectively, around pH 0-1. Therefore RNHCl can be assumed as the reactive species under the present investigations.

An α-amino acid is known to exist in the following equilibria in aqueous solutions.

Under the present experimental conditions the concentration of anion form will be very low and hence the possible reducing species may be either the cation form of amino acid or its zwitter ion S⁰. With the cation as the active species the derived rate law predicts a direct dependence on [H⁺] which is contrary to experimental evidence. Hence assuming S⁰ as the active species in the present investigations, Scheme-1 can be proposed to account for the observed kinetics.

SCHEME—I

Applying steady state treatment to X and S⁰ and with the reasonable assumption that k₋₁[H⁺] >> k₂

[RNHCl], the rate law

$$-\frac{d}{dt}[\text{CAT}] = \frac{k_1 k_2 [\text{SH}^+][\text{RNHCl}]}{k_{-1}[\text{H}^+]} \dots \dots (5)$$

can be derived in agreement with Equation.(1).

Effect of changing solvent composition :

In the present investigations a plot of log k_{obs} vs 1/D (D=Dielectric constant) gives a straight line (Fig. 3) with a negative slope indicating^{11,12} that CAT is reacting in neutral form and this supports the dipole-dipole interaction of Scheme—I.

Effect of chloride ion :

It is interesting to note that addition of chloride ion increases the rate of reaction. Such behaviour has been noticed in the Orton rearrangement of organic haloamines¹⁰. The following scheme can explain the observed kinetics :

SCHEME—II

If [CAT]_T represents total concentration of CAT, then

$$\begin{aligned} \text{rate} &= k_4 [\text{X}][\text{S}^0] \\ &= \frac{K k_4 [\text{Cl}^-][\text{CAT}]_T [\text{S}^0]}{1 + K[\text{Cl}^-]} \\ &= \frac{k_4 K k_1 [\text{Cl}^-][\text{CAT}]_T [\text{SH}^+]}{[\text{H}^+]\{1 + K[\text{Cl}^-]\}} \dots \dots (6) \end{aligned}$$

Since observed rate law is

$$\begin{aligned} -\frac{d}{dt}[\text{CAT}] &= k_{\text{obs}} \frac{[\text{CAT}][\text{SH}^+]}{[\text{H}^+]} \\ K_{\text{obs}} &= \frac{k_4 K k_1 \text{Cl}^-}{1 + K[\text{Cl}^-]} \\ \text{or } \frac{1}{k_{\text{obs}}} &= \frac{1 + K[\text{Cl}^-]}{k_4 K k_1 [\text{Cl}^-]} \\ &= \frac{1}{k_4 K k_1 [\text{Cl}^-]} + \frac{1}{k_4 k_1} \dots \dots (7) \end{aligned}$$

A double reciprocal plot of $1/k_{\text{obs}}$ vs $1/[\text{Cl}^-]$ gives a straight line (Fig. 4).

A detailed mechanism of oxidation is given in Scheme III.

The nitrile undergoes further reaction with the oxidant molecule and hydrolysis of the species would produce the cyanate.

The effect of H-bonding ensures considerable electron density at the amine nitrogen through the release of its non-bonding electrons. The enhanced nucleophilicity at the N-atom facilitates an electrophilic attack by the positive chlorine of RNHCl . This is more or less concerted with the release of H^+ ion and subsequent reactions take place through fast steps.

The mechanism is further supported by the fairly large values of the energy of activation for the formation of a more compact chlorinated amino acid activated complex. The negative entropy of activation observed during these reactions supports this contention. The values of thermodynamic

Fig. 4. Plot of $\log \frac{1}{k_{\text{obs}}} \text{ vs } \frac{1}{[\text{Cl}^-]}$.

(a) leucine, (b) serine, (c) glutamine and (d) glutamic acid.

$[\text{CAT}] = 0.003M$ for leucine, serine and glutamine and $0.001M$ for glutamic acid.

$[\text{Amino acid}] = 0.03M$ for leucine, serine and glutamic acid and $0.05M$ for glutamine.

$[\text{H}^+] = 0.05M$ for leucine and glutamine, $0.03M$ for serine and $0.01M$ for glutamic acid.

$\mu = 0.5M$; Temperature = 30° .

parameters are comparable to those obtained during the oxidation of glycine and valine⁴ by CAT.

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